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Management of the Library Socio-Cultural Activities in Terms of Information and Communication Changes

Abstract: *Introduction.* The relevance of the problem of managing the library's socio-cultural activities is associated with information and communication changes in society, which require the library practices formation, non-standard solutions development, the emergence of new ideas for library activities. *Purpose and methods.* The purpose of the article is to develop scientific provisions and practical recommendations for managing socio-cultural activities of the library in terms of information and communication changes. These changes will provide new opportunities for high-quality cross-border information interaction of library with users, simplify access to library resources and services simplify access to library resources and services and, as a result, promotes a positive image, improve the libraries' quality and efficiency. The methodological basis of the study is the dialectical principle of cognition, systemic, historical, terminological, cognitive, cultural approaches to the study of management processes of socio-cultural activities of the library during the period of information and communication changes in society. *Results.* The existing approaches to the terminology field of library science in different historical periods are systematized. The libraries' role and functions in the socio-cultural development of the individual are studied. Traditional and innovative types of activity in the central library system "Svichado" are determined, their efficiency is investigated. The sociological study results show that for effective library operation in the information and communication space, it is necessary to improve the skills of librarians and establish time norms that would regulate the activities of social networks. *Conclusions.* Management of libraries' socio-cultural activities, in the conditions of information and communication,

changes will allow reaching a new, high-quality level, and promotes the library development under the modern society requirements.

Keywords: information and communication changes, library, socio-cultural activities, Central Library System “Svichado”, socio-cultural projects, online projects, social networks.

1. Introduction

The problem formulation. The modern world is characterized by the emergence and introduction of a powerful information technology industry in all spheres of activity, which leads to information society creation. As stated in the Okinawa Charter on Global Information Society, information and communication technologies are one of the most important factors influencing the formation of the society in the 21st century (“Okinavskaya Khartiya”, 2000). The new stage in the information exchange processes development significantly affects the modern libraries'; activities nature, as the users'; demands and needs are more diverse. In this regard, an important task of our state is information infrastructure development, an adaptation of the library system to the network environment, and integration into the information and communication space.

The modern library requires an understanding of a new role in public life, realizing not only traditional tasks – providing users with books and other printed literature, but also innovative ones, mastering new technologies that ensure competitiveness in the market of information goods and services.

Today, the library sphere of Ukraine is on the periphery of state interests. The difficult economic situation of the country, the pressure of market relations on the socio-cultural sphere in general and libraries in particular, reforms, the number of which does not turn into quality, lack of development strategy and quality regulatory framework for libraries hampers their development as multidisciplinary and multifunctional institutions. Library activity in Ukraine is regulated by the Law of Ukraine “On Libraries and Library Affairs” (Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 2020), which states that libraries perform cultural, educational, and scientific functions.

The library network of Ukraine includes about 40,000 libraries of various types (public, technical, agricultural, medical, academic, educational, libraries of higher educational institutions, libraries for the blind) and different departmental subordination (state and municipal property, enterprises, organizations, and institutions).

Public libraries play a special role in realizing the various needs of the population in information, education, and culture in Ukraine. It is the most widespread social institution in the world, which is a democratic society deve-

lopment guarantor. As of January 1, 2019 (excluding the temporarily occupied Autonomous Republic of Crimea and the city of Sevastopol, and the territories of Donetsk and Luhansk regions), the network of public libraries of Ukraine numbered 15,662 institutions (libraries with branches), including four national, two state libraries and 15,656 communal public libraries of different levels (regional, district, urban, rural), which provide services to 11,208.1 thousand people. The network of rural libraries is 81% (12749 thousand) of the total number of public libraries (Yaroslav the Wise National Library of Ukraine, 2020).

Such a powerful network requires appropriate technical equipment. However, as of 2019, only 38% of public libraries have computers (5,949 institutions), and 30% provide users with Internet access (4,723 institutions). This negative trend is observed due to insufficient allocations for the library institutions' modernization. Thus, for the purchase of fixed assets (technical equipment, furniture, etc.) – in 2018, only 1% (28,252.3 thousand hryvnias) of the total amount of allocations for the institution's general budget fund was allocated.

The average indicator in Ukraine for one public library maintenance in 2018 was 174 thousand hryvnias, for one user – 246 hryvnias per year (Boiarynova, 2020). At the same time, libraries in Europe and the United States are considered as a platform that contributes to economic growth. According to research in Europe, on average, the libraries' ratio of profitability is 1 euro to 5.50 euros. That is, for every euro invested in the library, it returns 3.50 euros to citizens.

State study of the problem. Scientific sources review shows that the scientific literature covers a wide range of issues related to the use of innovative technologies in socio-cultural activities of the library, the use of modern tools, forms, methods of socio-cultural activities, staff development, and implementation of information and communication technologies. Thus, in the scientific works of scientists such as K. Abramov (2001), M. Afanasyev (1987), O. Bashun (1998), V. Bepalov (1997), N. Malynovska (1999), Yu. Melentyeva (1993), A. Pokrovskii (1922), A. Sokolov (1984) are described the most general theoretical and methodological approaches to the study of the historical development of municipal library systems. They define such concepts as “cultural and educational activities”, “leisure activities” and “socio-cultural activities” of the library. The main library functions as a socio-cultural center are determined.

The role of the library socio-cultural activities in educating the younger generation, its social significance for the creation, development, preservation, dissemination, and development of traditional folk culture values is revealed in the works of such domestic and foreign scholars as M. Berndtson (2012), T. Hbranchak (2019), V. Popyk (2015), R. Rubin (2004), R. Soichuk (2016), K. Wittenberg (2008), O. Vynohradova (2017), A. Zemskov (2016), S. Zozulia (2014).

Recently, many scientific works have appeared, in which more and more attention is paid to the organization and management of modern libraries' personnel. The scientific papers by C. Adams (2009), E. Bondarenko (2020), Y. Cherinet (2018), S. Holder and A. Lannon (2018, Ch. 2), T. Kostyrko (2016), M. Mahoney (2017), Ya. Martynyshyn and Ye. Kovalenko (2018), O. Serbin and Y. Kulyk (2019) discussed the problems of staffing libraries; HR management directions are analyzed: personnel assessment; training directions, training, and library staff motivation; the role of staff in improving the quality and efficiency of libraries has been identified. Scientists have noticed that today it is no longer enough to pay attention only to the correct selection of personnel, but it is also necessary to deal with the issue of revealing hidden potential through the professional and personal development of creative workers who can implement their knowledge and skills in practice, to adapt to the rapidly changing conditions of the present.

The scientific works of J. Frumkin (2005), E. Guseva (2010), L. Pisarenko (2019), T. Sydorenko and A. Fihura (2019), E. Wenger et al. (2002) consider various options for modern libraries' development, the digital library phenomenon, the libraries systems promotion. Numerous practices of modeling information and communication technologies O. Klymenko (2016), T. Kolesnykova (2012), O. Lystopad (2018), O. Onyshchenko (2014), I. Perederii (2016), O. Vasylenko (2016) were used in library science and influenced the reproduction of new information and communication models of library activities.

Unresolved issues. The research topic complexity led to a significant source base involvement, which consisted of domestic and foreign experts' scientific works. Paying tribute to the scientific achievements of scientists, whose works are an important basis for analyzing the socio-cultural activities of libraries in the information space, it is worth noting that the modern terminology field of library science and the practice of modern libraries activities operate in a wide range of concepts, require clarification at a new stage in the development of information exchange processes.

Issues related to the material and technical condition of libraries, their socio-cultural functions transformation, and the lack of a holistic system of professional staff motivation that would cover all socio-economic and psychological aspects of the library workers' functioning in current conditions remain insufficiently unresolved.

A necessary condition for solving these problems is the library's socio-cultural management system analysis in the information exchange process based on modern technologies. Modernization of the management component will allow mastering a new paradigm of socio-cultural policy, based on

focused activities to form, satisfy and increase the users' socio-cultural needs. The relevance and importance of addressing these issues determined the purpose and objectives of the study.

2. Purpose and methods

The purpose and research tasks. The purpose of the article is to develop scientific provisions and practical recommendations for managing the socio-cultural activities of the library in the context of information and communication changes. That changes will provide new opportunities for high-quality cross-border information interaction of the library with users, simplify access to library resources and services, and, as a result, contribute to the formation of a positive image, increase the quality and efficiency of libraries.

Achieving this purpose has made it necessary to solve the following tasks:

- to reveal the essence and significance of libraries' socio-cultural activities in the spiritual enrichment of visitors;
- to determine the role and functions of the library in the individual socio-cultural development;
- to offer directions of modern library effective management in the conditions of information and communication changes.

Methodology and methods. The methodological basis of the study is the dialectical principle of cognition, systemic, historical, terminological, cognitive, cultural approaches to the study of management processes of socio-cultural activities of the library in the period of information and communication changes in society. The research is based on the study of historical events in chronological order to identify internal and external links, patterns, and contradictions in the formation and development of library activities. The conceptual apparatus, terminological variability, and the conceptual content of the socio-cultural activity of the library in different historical periods are considered. The management of socio-cultural activities of libraries is investigated from the point of view of a systemic approach, according to which the library is a holistic system consisting of interconnected and interacting subsystems and individual elements, which are united by a common goal aimed at ensuring the effective satisfaction of the needs of all parties to the socio-cultural process.

The study pays special attention to the cognitive principle of cognition and because today, the library's socio-cultural activities require the study of dynamics and its relationship with the informational and cognitive needs of society. The role and functions of libraries in the individual's socio-cultural

development are considered through the prism of the culture and cultural values. Human develops not only based on his mastery of culture but also replenishes it with new elements. In this regard, the assimilation of cultural values is the development of man himself and his formation as a creative person, which allows a deeper understanding of the role of socio-cultural activities of the library and the need to develop its management in times of information and communication change.

The theoretical and methodological basis of the study were the provisions of the management theory, legislative and regulatory acts of Ukraine, monographs, scientific articles of domestic and foreign scientists on the management of the socio-cultural activities of libraries in the context of information and communication changes. The work uses both general scientific and special research methods, in particular: terminological – when studying scientific literature sources, legislative and other regulatory legal acts regarding the public libraries functioning; historical and logical – to study the genesis and analysis of the library science evolution; theoretical generalization and comparison – for development of a conceptual framework of the concepts “cultural work”, “mass work”, “cultural and leisure activities”, “leisure activity”, “socio-cultural activities of library”; the method of analysis and synthesis was used in the study of traditional and innovative forms and methods of work of modern libraries; logical – to justify the feasibility of modernizing the activities of libraries; statistical – when analyzing the current state of library work; the observation method was used during the employees questionnaire of the Central District Library of the Central Library System “Svichado”; survey method – to assess the effectiveness of material incentives for library staff and photochronometry methods – when developing time standards for library workers to work in social networks.

Information base. The information base of the study was the scientific works of famous domestic and foreign scientists on library science and the practice of libraries, as well as legislative and regulatory acts of Ukraine that regulate the public libraries' functioning. Official materials of the State Statistics Service of Ukraine, data of the Central Library System “Svichado” on the activities of libraries included in its composition and reporting materials of the Central District Library of the Central Library System “Svichado” on the effectiveness of the introduction of innovative forms and methods of work. Reference literature, information resources of the World Wide Web, as well as the results of the author's research were used.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Socio-cultural activity of the library: terminological variability

One of the urgent tasks of modern society is the organization of useful, constructive leisure activities of the population, which can be considered a phenomenon of culture and has a value-meaning content and a functional purpose. The formation of libraries' socio-cultural activity took place in the conditions of the society's socio-historical rebirth, under the influence of the transformation of public, social, and spiritual values in various historical periods. The study of libraries' socio-cultural activities makes it possible to highlight the main historical stages that had formulated the corresponding terminological field in library science.

For the second half of the 19th century – 1917, book publishing development, the creation of libraries, reading rooms, and the formation of library collections is characteristic. During this period, libraries conducted cultural and educational activities, which included literary, musical evenings, con-certs, theater performances, scientific lectures, and meetings with prominent personalities.

Since 1917, the next stage of libraries' development in our country begins, which provides an increase in citizens' cultural and educational level, influencing the national, patriotic, and aesthetic education of society. The large-scale socio-cultural activities of libraries began in 1920 when the cultural and educational work of the library provided for the promotion of the illiteracy elimination and cultural and educational level improvement of the population. If in 1917 the libraries satisfied the needs of 8-10% of the urban population, then in 1920 they were used by all educated people (Rozovyk, 2004, p. 13). At this stage of development, the library science terminological field was replenished with such a concept as “cultural work”. By the cultural work of the library, V. Nevskii (1925, p. 53) understood several special events aimed at increasing the issuance of books and increasing the benefits of reading them.

In the 1920s and 1930s, libraries were seen as centers of culture that were used for political and educational activities and the development of self-education. Mass forms of library activity are becoming widespread: holidays organization, music evenings, literary events, where books were discussed and writers were met, children's literary and play activities were organized, interest groups were created, which were mostly political in nature.

With the accumulation of experience in mass work, the population cultural and educational level growth, in the 1950s and 1970s, new types of activities

(exhibition, organizational: mass events preparation and holding, a celebration of anniversary events, historical dates) are developed, and the concept of “cultural and mass work” of the library appears. However, in mass and exhibition activities, political propaganda remained one of the means of communist education.

After the adoption of the “Regulation on Public Libraries” at the First Library Congress of the Russian Soviet Federative Socialist Republic, the concept of “libraries mass work” (Smushkova, 1927, p. 8), which in the 70-80s was finally fixed in the terminology dictionaries and scientific improvements of many researchers, becomes widespread. The first interpretations of the term “libraries mass work” were published in the “Dictionary of Library Terms” (Chubaryan, 1976), “Handbook of the Librarian” (Antonova & Semenova, 1985, pp. 108-112), and presented in the terminological dictionary “Library Studies”. In the dictionary, the mass work of the library is defined as a set of forms and methods of oral and visual propaganda of printed works and other documents among readers and the public (Suslova & Ulanova, 1986, p. 79).

Since the late 1980s of the twentieth century, in the works of foreign and domestic cultural scientists, the concept of “mass” has acquired a negative meaning. In libraries, work is carried out in playful forms. Library theaters are created and functioning, work is carried out on aesthetic education and active involvement of young people.

Since the early 1990s, libraries have been actively using a range of effective socio-cultural and leisure forms of work. This contributed to the terminological enrichment of library science with the concepts of “cultural and leisure activities”, “leisure activity”, “socio-cultural activity”.

In modern scientific publications, the most commonly used terms are the concept of “cultural and leisure activities”, which A. Zharkov (2002, p. 34) understands as a purposeful process of creating conditions for motivated personal choice of subject activity, which promotes the assimilation, preservation, production, and dissemination of spiritual and material values in the field of leisure. T. Lovkova (2004) considers that this concept characterizes “the purposeful and structured activity of libraries connected with formation, satisfaction, and raising of spiritual needs of users to comprehensively and harmoniously develop the personality in the leisure space”.

The concept of leisure activity of libraries differs in the functions related to the formation, satisfaction, development, and rise of various cultural needs of a person (in communication, recreation, creativity, play), which contribute to the development of the user's personality in leisure space (Matlina, 1988, p. 11). Modern library scholars consider leisure as a synonym for free time.

G. Avanesova (2006, p. 13) defines the leisure activities of the library as appropriately organized and meaningful activity in the free time of a person or group of people, which develops based on human needs, as well as following the goals of recreation and socio-cultural development.

The term “socio-cultural activity of libraries” became widespread at the turn of the twentieth and 21st centuries. Although, the beginnings of socio-cultural activity can be found in ancient libraries (this, particularly, is the spatial and architectural solution of library buildings, the general organization of library work, the meaning of libraries as treasures of knowledge in the life of ancient society). Since the 20th century, libraries' socio-cultural activity has been considered a valuable factor in the cultural policy implementation, a means of adapting people to the environment and communication, regulating and broadcasting national and universal human culture in its various manifestations (Vizhichanina, 2018).

The essence of the concept of library socio-cultural activity is also being discussed among many scholars. Thus, A. Kovalchuk (2000) considers this term as a social phenomenon characterized by a set of relationships, activities carried out by specific forms, methods, and means based on interests manifested by the individual in cultural life, interaction and communication of people in their free time. According to the definition of a library scholar, A. Sokolov (2003) – it is the cultural activity of social actors (professional and non-professional social groups) to create cultural values, develop the abilities of individuals and serve their creative activities; communications aimed at the dissemination, storage and public use of all types of cultural property.

It has been found out that today the library science is considered a socio-cultural system, and the library is one of the most important socio-cultural institutions of society (Pashyn, 2005). Against the background of the evolution of political, economic, and social conditions, the development of information technologies, the socio-cultural activities of libraries take on a multi-level character and creative approach. The library can reasonably be defined as an integrative social institution containing information, documentary and cultural components, acts in the interests of society, the state, and society as a whole, to create, preserve, and disseminate cultural values. The phenomenon of the library as a socio-cultural institution is that communication, given the constant development of information technology, becomes a strategic element in the socio-cultural activities of the library.

3.2. Role and functions of libraries in socio-cultural development of personality

Libraries, which today are social institutions, are created to meet the information, educational, scientific, cultural, and other needs of users, ensure citizens various rights to library services, access to cultural values, disseminate knowledge and information, promote democratization and humanization of society, develop education and culture, enrich the spiritual potential of citizens. Libraries are both social and cultural institutions. As a social institution, they organize the collection and distribution of documents to meet the information needs of users; as a cultural institution – they accumulate and translate cultural experience.

The general functions of socio-cultural activities of libraries are the following:

- informational and educational (opportunity to meet informational, spiritual, cultural, and aesthetic needs);
- educational (assimilation of systematic knowledge that increases the social status, prestige, self-esteem of a person and change the worldview);
- creative (opportunity to show creative talents); there are leisure or recreational (full use of free time, meaningful rest of users);
- communicative and organizational (realization of the need for communication and mutual exchange of useful information);
- general cultural (raising the educational and cultural level of the population, preservation, and development of national culture).

Today's socio-cultural activities of libraries have partially inherited the forms and methods of work from previous historical periods of their existence. Such classic forms of work remained: library funds collection in all branches of knowledge and the maintenance of catalogs' system; record-keeping, storage and use of documents; library users' information support, information services provision; cultural and educational activities (excursions); facilitating the organization of the educational process (lectures, seminars, round tables, conferences); mass events organization, arrangement of book-illustrative exhibitions, other events of literature popularization.

Over the long period of their history, libraries have accumulated significant experience in leisure activities, implementing its various directions and using variable forms. However, the new stage in the development of information exchange processes greatly affects the choice of the library mission and functions, approaches to the formation of library and information resources and user services, the development of library technologies, the modernization of traditional and development of new strategic directions.

Analyzing the library's activity experience, it should be noted that in foreign countries, first of all in Western Europe and the USA, online bookstores, book, and literary cafes, Internet cafes, Internet clubs, social and cultural leisure centers rendering socio-cultural services are widely popular (consulting bureaus, psychological trainings, maternal groups, meetings with sports coaches and social teachers, family evenings of rest, educational and informative work: courses, creative classes, and workshops) in real and virtual mode (Bocheliuk, 2006). Thus, innovative forms of work become the determining factor in the effectiveness of modern libraries' socio-cultural activities. Innovations are the result of library modernization; implementation of new ideas in libraries requires the creation of conditions for the modern technologies introduction, which are considered as “a set of methods, tools, and measures that ensure innovation” (Kachanova, 2003).

The centralized library system “Svichado” of the Department of Culture and Cultural Heritage Protection of the Sviatoshynskiy District State Administration in Kyiv is in the constant search of new forms and technologies in library services, positioning itself as a polyfunctional and multidisciplinary institution that creates comfortable conditions for providing services to users, including in quarantine conditions associated with countering coronavirus infection of COVID-19. The centralized library system “Svichado” is a budget non-profit organization funded by the budget of the city of Kyiv and unites the libraries of the Sviatoshynskiy district of the city of Kyiv into a single structural and integral entity. Libraries that are part of the Centralized Library System “Svichado” (Central District Library of the Centralized Library System “Svichado”; O. Blok, O. Herzen, Magtymguly, V. Stefanyk, Nathan Rybak libraries, “Dzherelo” library, libraries for children “Knyzhkova Svitlytsia” (“Book Chamber”), “Prominets” (“Ray”), and M. Dubov library) have the status of public libraries (*Figure 1*).

In 2017, the city pilot project “Library-HUB” was launched based on the Central District Library of the Centralized Library System “Svichado”, which provides for the modernization of material and technical base and library space (*Figure 2*), and not only for the main function of the library (library and information service) but also for the organization of exhibition galleries, theater and literary studios, board games and gaming tournaments, workshops, trainings, seminars, webinars, journalism, video lectures).

As a result of the old library modernization, users received a new format of library – the epicenter of socio-cultural events, the center of productive work, study, leisure; public usable space with a mobile furniture system, the possibility of connecting to the Internet anywhere in the room, with access to electronic information databases of public libraries at all levels.

Figure 1. Structure of the Centralized Library System "Svichado"

Source: own development

The zoning of the library space makes it possible to provide comfortable service to users according to their needs. At the disposal of visitors, there is a common public space with an interactive hall with 60 seats, equipped with a complex of technical facilities for video views, presentations; information, intellectual and lounge areas, MiniBib for children, meeting room, library printing base, equipped with the latest technical facilities (computer equipment, copy machines, printers, laminating machines, 3D printer), places for individual work with PCs and study, work of people with physical health features.

Thus, innovative socio-cultural technologies, which are designed to change and complement the traditional libraries' activities, store evidence of the past and at the same time dynamically respond to the changing situation in the world.

The introduction of modern technologies opens opportunities for more effective users' service, search for new library activity directions.

Figure 2. Photo collage of the modernized Central District Library of the Centralized Library System “Svichado”

Source: own development

On the basis of the Central District Library of the Centralized Library System “Svichado”, there are courses on the basics of computer literacy, the purpose of which is to master the basic skills of computer and electronic gadgets: PCs, laptops, tablets, e-books; free use of Internet resources to fulfill requests, payment of utilities and the like.

At the present stage of innovative activity of the Central Library System “Svichado” actively implements socio-cultural projects. Within the framework of social partnership with the Charitable Foundation “With Warmth in the Heart”, the Central District Library of the Centralized Library System “Svichado”

began the project “Library – Territory of Kindness”, aimed at ensuring meaningful leisure, developing reading interests and information services for children with special health features. “Fairy tale therapy: What Can a Fairy Tale Do?” fairy tale therapy for adults with N. Povarova participation. The project “On your mark, Biblio Prodlonka” started at the beginning of 2020 and provides home task preparation for children of junior and middle grades. And well as the projects “Joy of inspiration – for everyone!”; “Gamification”.

The organization of conferences, seminars, round tables, lectures is also a form of innovative socio-cultural activity of the Central District Library of the Centralized Library System “Svichado”. With the help of modern technology, students and teachers of the Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts were able to attend and make presentations at scientific events of the university (recently, the most significant were the IV International Scientific and Practical Conference “Creative Technologies, Entrepreneurship and Management in the Organization of the Socio-Cultural Sphere of the Twentieth Century” (October 14-15, 2020), IV All-Ukrainian Round Table “Problems and Prospects for the Development of Management and Management Education in the Socio-Cultural Sphere” (December 2, 2020) and the V All-Ukrainian Scientific and Methodological Seminar “Formation of the modern paradigm of management-education in the socio-cultural sphere” (April 6-7, 2021), organized by the Department of Fashion and Show Business.

With the beginning of quarantine restrictions related to countering Coronavirus infection, COVID-19, all reference, information, cultural, educational, research and leisure activities of the library have moved to the online plane. The Central District Library of the Centralized Library System “Svichado” has begun active work on promoting educational, informative, leisure online resources, video lessons, online exhibitions, virtual visits to museums and historical sites, and more. New interesting projects have been established: “Conversations with a psychologist”; “Learning to draw online”; “Out of Quarantine Reading”; “Literary Horoscope”; “English Online”; “Cultural quarantine: what to read?”; Audio-lib “Listen to books in Ukrainian”; “Book Chamber” and others.

During the first half of 2020, 1353 mass events, promotions (including online) were held in the Central Library System “Svichado” which were attended by more than 7476 users. The Central Library System “Svichado” is actively entering the virtual space, creating its pages on Facebook and Instagram. These forms are certainly promising, especially in working with young people. During this period, the site of the Central Library System “Svichado” (<http://svichado.kiev.ua/>) was visited by more than 71,000 users, which indicates that the libraries have aroused widespread interest, gained popularity, expanded the field of cultural communications in local society.

3.3. Effective management of the modern library in the context of information and communications changes

Today, the library organizes socio-cultural communication processes in cyberspace, which requires new approaches to personnel management. The readiness to change and transform the library itself as a socio-cultural institution depends on the level of professional competence, skills, experience, self-organization, and self-government of employees. A modern library worker should successfully use new information technologies, be able to evaluate information, and have an algorithm for searching and selecting information in Internet resources.

On the basis of the Central District Library of the Centralized Library System “Svichado” (Table 1, 2) a survey of employees was conducted, in which all library employees took part, who hold such positions as director, deputy director, head of the library, head of the department, head of the sector, chief librarian, chief engineer, leading librarian, librarian of the 1st and 2nd category, librarian. In addition to questionnaires, research methods such as observation and conversation were used.

Table 1. Base salaries and wages of Central library system “Svichado” employees as of 01.09.2020

Job title	Category	Base Salary	Supplement for the length of service	Surcharge for working conditions 50%	Wage
Director	15	5741.00	1722.30	2870.50	10333.80
Deputy director	15	5454.00	1636.20	2727.00	9817.20
Head of the library	14	5385.00	1292.00	2692.50	9369.5
Head of the department	13	5051.00	1030.60	2525.5	8607.10
Head of the sector	12	4717.00	943.40	2358.50	8018.9
Chief librarian	12	4717.00	471.70	2358.50	7547.20
Leading librarian	12	4717.00	1415.10	2358.50	8490.60
Librarian of the 1st category	11	4383.00	2169.50	2191.50	8744
Librarian of the 2nd category	10	4050.00	607.50	2025.00	6682.5
Librarian	9	3849.00	962.25	1924.50	6735.75

Source: developed on the basis of the site of the Central Library System “Svichado” (<http://svichado.kiev.ua/>)

Table 2. Rationing the time of library workers to work on social networks

Process name	Unit of measurement	Norm time
Writing a post: collecting information, writing text, selecting images, working in a Photoshop editor, posting	1 post	90 min.
Stories posting: collecting information, writing text, selecting illustrations, videos, posting surveys	1 story	30 min.
Live broadcasting: selection of interesting information, answers to questions	1 broadcast(stream)	120min.
		live (on air)
Posting an information message about the events of the library: photographing the event, writing the text, repost	1 event	120 min.
Posting information about novelties of literature: selection of new items, compiling an abstract of the publication	1 information material	120 min.
Preparation and posting of advertising information	1 advertising information	90 min.
Page traffic monitoring, reaction tracking, responses to comments on the message	1 monitoring	20 min.

Source: developed by the author

The data obtained as a result of the questionnaire helped: to identify problems on certain issues and areas of the library as a whole; analyze employees' attitudes to work, working conditions, team climate, and motivation system; track changes that have occurred in the library activities as a result of the quarantine restrictions introduction.

It is determined that the material remuneration of the library staff is fixed according to the tariffs of the Unified Tariff Grid, and the director of the library cannot influence the size of the official salary.

Most library workers complain that they experience financial difficulties when their wages expire much earlier than the next one. Consequently, wages are not aimed at fully fulfilling the stimulating function. However, 90% of respondents value the guarantees of socio-economic stability and social protection, are also satisfied with their professional duties, and consider the work of the librarian to be fascinating and creative because for most employees the Central District Library of the Centralized Library System “Svichado” is an alma mater. Employees also noted that special advantage is a modern material and technical support of the workplace and the moral and psychological climate in the team.

Since professional development plays a crucial role in professional activities, the questionnaire block dealt with the library workers' advanced training

problems. In addition, survey participants were asked to assess their level of knowledge in working online. Employees of the Central District Library of the Centralized Library System “Svichado” noted that in the first half of 2020, 6 meetings were held with librarians from different regions of Ukraine. During the online meetings, the issues of the need to expand the libraries' activities in the online space were discussed. Librarians shared their experience in holding online conferences, mass events, got acquainted with the experience of a librarian from the United States – Elizabeth White.

The survey questions also related to the daily cost of working time for maintaining a page on social networks, content topics, and the publications' frequency. The Central District Library of the Centralized Library System “Svichado” has a responsible person who provides support and information content for the resources of information representation in social media. However, the effectiveness of the library's socio-cultural work largely depends on the involvement degree of all staff members. To do this, it is necessary to develop methodical recommendations for the implementation in the Central District Library of the Centralized Library System “Svichado” of work time standards, which are carried out in social networks.

Posting information about the library, not only on the site but also on social media pages, reflects its status in society and establishes communication, especially with young people. Work on high-quality and effective management of pages on social networks is an important component of the socio-cultural activity of the institution, so library workers need to systematically improve their skills for effective work on social networks, and managers need to document qualification requirements, job responsibilities, and time standards for working with social networks. For employees, it is necessary to regularly conduct such types of training sessions as lectures, seminars and practical classes, trainings, business games, master classes, discussions, round tables, analysis of specific situations when working on social networks. The development of communication and information space in library activities will allow the library to reach a new, high-quality level, develop under the requirements of modern society and expand communication links.

4. Conclusions

Ensuring the successful socio-cultural activities of the library in terms of information and communication changes requires the use of modern management solutions. The results of the study provide the following conclusions and suggestions:

1. The terminological field of library science and practice of libraries activities for the organization of leisure of the population operate with a wide

range of the concepts “cultural work”, “mass work”, “cultural and leisure activities”, “leisure activity”, “socio-cultural activity”, related to formation of the state cultural policy during various periods of historical development.

2. The library can reasonably be defined as an integrative social institution containing information, documentary and cultural components, acts in the interests of the community, state, and society as a whole, to create, preserve, and disseminating cultural values. The phenomenon of the library as a socio-cultural institute is that communication, given the continuous development of information technologies, becomes a strategic element in the socio-cultural activities of the library.

3. The purpose of modern libraries is to create an information culture and ensure equal access to intellectual, spiritual, and creative development to meet the users' needs using new information and communication technologies. Today's socio-cultural activities of libraries have partially inherited forms and methods of work from the previous historical periods of their existence (exhibition work, excursions, scientific events), as well as mastered new work strategies.

3.1. The “Svichado” Central Library System is a non-profit, state-owned institution funded by the Kyiv budget. The “Svichado” Central Library System unites seven adults, two children's, and one youth library. In 2017, the Central District Library of the Centralized Library System “Svichado”, based on a project of the Kyiv City Government, was completely modernized and provided with modern facilities, which provides opportunities for more efficient customer service and finding new directions in library activities.

3.2. The socio-cultural activities of the Central District Library of the Centralized Library System “Svichado” are multifaceted, including various areas of reference, information, cultural and educational, research and leisure activities. With the beginning of quarantine restrictions, the library moved to the online plane and mastered new strategies, namely: organization and implementation of socially important cultural projects in the online space (video lessons, online exhibitions, virtual visits to museums and historical sites, etc.), using new information and media technology. The innovative activity of the library intensifies its work and attracts the attention of new users.

4. Library staff today need to be considered as an important resource in the current stage of library services transformation, which needs to be properly managed and create conditions for its development. The analysis of the employees' questionnaire of the Central District Library of the Centralized Library System “Svichado” makes it possible to state that it is necessary to look for new, scientifically-based approaches for reforming salary and incentive scheme. At the same time, the employees noted that a special advantage in their work is the modern material and technical support of the workplace, the moral and psychological climate in the team, exciting and creative work.

5. Social networks are an important tool for the library's presence in the virtual information and communication space. The effectiveness of their use in practice requires continuous improvement of the specialists' skills in the library and information sphere following the objectives of the information society formation. The development of normative documents regulating library activities in social networks would be a significant step in socio-communicative interaction with users.

The scientific novelty. The scientific novelty of the research results is that for the first time: a scientific approach has been suggested to manage the libraries' activities in the information and communication environment to improve the quality and effectiveness of their work. The research methodology on the rationalization of time for work performed on social networks was further developed, which will allow documenting qualification requirements, job responsibilities, norms, and remuneration for library workers administering in the network information and communication space.

The significance of the study. The obtained research results are the basis for solving practical problems regarding the impact of information and communication changes on the socio-cultural activities of the library. The main provisions of the study can be used by the head of the library and will contribute to improving the quality and efficiency of library workers in the information and communication space, causing resonance in public.

Prospects for further research. Further research should focus on the status and trends of the library's human resources, develop a strategy for motivating library workers and develop a system of continuing library education.

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